

Modernity and tradition in the work of Luis Peña Ganchegui.

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Abstract

Born in Oñate in 1962 and educated as an architect in Madrid, Luis Peña Ganchegui returned to the Basque Country determined to repay his country for the education received, rewarding those who had enthusiastically sacrificed themselves for him. This mission will eventually become the need to join the dictates of modernity with the teachings of tradition, paying attention to some roots whose personal interpretation, indebted to his highly-regarded Pio Baroja, will result in the flourishing of a new way of doing architecture in the Basque Country

A deliberate assertion of his origins will accompany the architect in his evolution from the modern abstract space (typical of his early years of academic training) to the existential place of Organicism (in line with the revisionist turning point of modernism). This evolution will lead him to accentuate his own personal style, identified with his homeland and origins, and which will be reflected in his architectural works and which can be regarded as a sum of episodes of the same research in which any new project conveys elements imported from the former ones.

After his first experiences in the late 50's, shared with Juan Manuel Encio, following the dictates of the Modern Movement, Peña felt the need to adapt his architectural work to the special character of the sites he acted on, contributing with it to the making of the place. This need, clearly expressed in his early interventions in Motrico, will be accentuated after a brief period of time as City Architect of San Sebastián, following his intervention in *Plaza de la Trinidad*, which was carried out in 1963. It is in this very same year that Jorge Oteiza published his book *Quosque Tandem...! Essay on the Aesthetic Interpretation of the Basque Soul*, which supports the existence of the so-called Basque style reflecting the specific cultural and historic character of the Basque people, and which triggered the process of cultural and artistic reconstruction of the Basque Country, based on the so-much wanted Basque School of Contemporary Art, in which Luis Peña himself actively participated as head of the architectural dimension.

Peña's approach to the environment where he grew up, rather than being superficial or anecdotal following traditional or folkloric associations, is expressed in his search for a connection with universal solutions in agreement with modernity. By means of a repertoire of recurrent elements in his works (such as articulation, the concept of layered envelope, the continuity between roof and façade, unity of material, reductionism...) Peña Ganchegui will carry out a review of the modern principles, pursuing its same objectives but bearing in mind the teachings of the past and the specific circumstances of each process. This approach, in line with what was later called critical regionalism, is handled by Peña providing traditional based solutions, whose result, despite referring to content rather than form, also shows formal connotations with the Basqueness, as it is developed through a sober and radical style coinciding with that of other artists of his country.

Keywords: Luis Peña Ganchegui, Tradition, Modernity, Basque Architecture, Critical Regionalism.

Introduction

When Rafael Moneo pointed out, in the first catalogue compiling an anthology of Luis Peña Ganchegui's work¹, that the construction of *Torre Vista Alegre* (fig. 1) had been a turning point in the architect's approach to architecture, he described it as an early work, typical of a newly graduate: 'a modern work in which the confidence and firmness of the way the volume manifested itself and the ability to manipulate the complex interior spaces stood out'.²

(Fig. 1) Torre Vista Alegre (Zarauz, 1958). Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

For Moneo, Zarauz's tower meant a special way of understanding architecture, which regards works as 'autonomous objects, oblivious to the environment, depending just on the logic its design lies on' whose autistic nature, in Moneo's view, had to distress Luis Peña. A distress that would make him question if that was the architecture the site required, and made him consider the need to 'have more respect for the purposes and aims one wishes to realize with the creation of a work as well as the circumstances characterising the physical environment in which a work is erected, in short, to propose a diverse architecture'. This diverse architecture would be no other than the one his homeland, his own country required; a familiar environment, whose limits and rules arise both from society and the landscape.

And although Moneo was right to highlight the change, obvious if you revise Peña's career, he was too hasty in pointing out the way it happened, since it was neither so sudden nor was it due to the impact of that early work on the landscape. The truth is that even though the idea of a newly graduated young architect implementing a theoretical model, learned at school and totally oblivious to his environment, after having lived in Madrid for a decade, and that it was this contrast with this environment which put him on the right track, may seem charming and plausible, it is clear that neither the theoretical model was so abstract nor the years spent away from the Basque Country had had such a big impact on his spirit so as to make him feel a stranger in his own homeland.

The image of the slender tower on the slope of Zarauz, rather than have a negative impact on a spirit eager to reinvest in his country the knowledge acquired during his training in Madrid³, meant an important boost to his career⁴. In fact, *this building*, so apparently debtor to Le Corbusier, far from being autistic, contains some elements representative of the teachings of Organicism, such as its articulated half-floors, its lay-out adapted to the environment and, mainly, its connection with the environment, incorporating a transition porch between the inside and outside of the building. As we will see, the evolution seen in Peña's career, from his early proposals which could be considered academic (as the rationalist and functionalist principles learned at school are implemented mimetically) to the forging of his own discourse connecting the key principles of modernity with the necessary reference to his country and vernacular tradition, takes place gradually during the early years of his career and is favoured by the conditioning factors of the locations he acts on.

Background

Born in Oñate into a family native of Motrico, Peña spent his childhood between his hometown, a representative example of the inland towns of Guipúzcoa, and his parents' town, a typical fishing town of the many found on the Basque coast. Thus, being very knowledgeable of the two archetypes of rural communities prevailing in the Basque country, that of the valley and that of the coast, with its distinctive features (made up of isolated compact communities, placed around a central point, the former, whereas the latter is more gothic, developed organically by addition) young Peña was to incorporate the identity of his homeland and the teachings of its tradition to the discourse of modernity acquired during his training years at the School of Architecture in Madrid.

But, in order for this communion between popular wisdom and the illustration represented by rationalist abstraction, to take place, there had to be, apart from his life experience and academic training, at least two other fundamental elements. On the one hand, the vision of Basqueness provided by Pio Baroja⁵, whose literary circle he frequented during his university training, and on the other hand, the revisionist context which, with regard to the modern movement, Team X boosted in post-war European architecture.

The socio-political context of the time when Peña started his career (at the change of decade from the 50's to the 60's, at the dawn of development which announced a mild open-door tendency in the closeness of Franco's regime), together with the interest of Catalonia and Madrid's architects to promote and support the architectural scene by means of frequent meetings (the so-called *Pequeños Congresos de Arquitectura*, started in 1959) led Peña to head the renovation of Basque architecture demanding for his country a leading role in the updating and adaptation of the Spanish architecture to the international context. The glory days of the 20's and 30's (under the leadership of Labayen, Aizpurua and Vallejo who belonged to the north group of GATEPAC)⁶ were cut short first by the civil war and then by the subsequent isolation. That glorious past supported the renovation claim which Peña assumed as soon as he could, participating in the second call for the *Pequeños Congresos* meeting held in Barcelona in the spring of 1960, and leading the organisation of the third held in San Sebastian in the same year's autumn.⁷

(Fig. II) 8 viviendas Ramírez (Donostia, 1962). Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

Modernity versus tradition

Brought up in an environment in which buildings were made up of walled structures and heavy half-timbered, and covered in tile roofs projecting beyond the façade line producing wide eaves, Peña identified modernity with the abstract geometries of the avant-garde painters, (the basic volumes of the Modern Movement) and with the lightness and transparency of the images illustrated in the few foreign magazines he could have access to as an undergraduate. A collection of images compatible with the principles of the Modern Movement, which, regarding collective residential architecture (the only subject he will deal with in his early career) had resulted in the implementation of new settlements based on linear half height apartment blocks.⁸

The problem for Peña, when it comes to implementing the lessons learned, lies in the fact that, although some of the elements deriving from Le Corbusier's principles, such as the use of *pilotis* and the free designing of the ground plan, might be accepted in his designs as were in agreement with the environment, those associated with the flat roof, the free design of façade and the horizontal windows, which he incorporated in his first projects, were difficult to fit in the environment of Guipúzcoa owing to adverse weather conditions and a collective culture

strongly opposed to abstraction. This will make him, from the early days of his career, raise the issue of the need to incorporate inclined roofing to his buildings as an absolute basic principle, and will lead him to consider carefully how to address the building envelope, which will result in formulations based on superimposing layers.

As I have already mentioned, the evolution in Peña, from a modern abstract space faithful to the most orthodox rationalist principles (learned early in his academic training), towards the existentialist place characteristic of the Organicism (in agreement with the revisionist approach of the Modern movement)⁹, was not sudden or occurred after the construction of *Torre Vista Alegre*. Proof of this is the fact that in the projects immediately after his first work, we can find features similar to those which presumably had brought him in the wrong direction, including autonomous blocks of pseudo-Brutalist language and a second tower, more slender than the one in Zarauz, in the centre of Motrico. Quite the contrary, Peña will find *the right direction* progressively, approaching his work as continuous research, in which every new project will provide new progress based on the achievements obtained from previous tests.

This special manner of blending tradition and modernity, which will accompany Peña during his entire career, will be formulated from 1964 with the definition of four very personal and archetypical works, (Fig. III): *12 viviendas Urresti*, *24 viviendas, Aizetzu and Casa Imanolena*, in Motrico, and *6 viviendas Arrigain*, in Oyarzun, and will further develop until his acclamation with the construction of *Plaza del Tenis* (Donostia, 1975). But the making of these 4 foundational projects and the subsequent development could not be explained without the existence of a transition period, whose beginning can be dated to 1961 with the construction of *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua*¹⁰ in Motrico, and which ended in 1963 coinciding with his intervention in *Plaza de la Trinidad* in San Sebastián. A stage in which the Basque architect gets involved in the search for that 'new living tradition' to which José Antonio Coderch referred in 1961 on the pages of *Domus* magazine, claiming architects 'with a cord tied to their feet so that they can not go far away from the land where they have their roots and from the people they know better'.¹¹

(Fig. III) The works designed in 1964 (Urresti, Aizetzu, Imanolena and Arrigain) and Plaza del Tenis. Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

The change of perspective from a work focussed on the architectural objects to another in which architecture intertwines with the environment, is going to be boosted in Peña's case by the associations and characteristics of the environment where the works he made during the period mentioned above were developed. The one which opens this period, being the trigger and precursor, is the one we want to analyse when it comes to establishing the relationship between modernity and tradition in his whole work.

A pioneering work

If there is one aspect exemplifying Peña's search for blending modernity and tradition this is his wish to represent abstraction using specific elements of vernacular architecture, as it is particularly reflected in the integration of pitched roof into modern architectural practice. A first approach to both aspects of vernacular architecture practice can be found in the work *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua* in 1961.

It is the first work he did in the town centre of Motrico, and he will erect it on a site owned by his family. Namely, the building stands on the site occupied by the orchard of his family, next to the *Asunción* church, the massive neoclassic structure dominating Churruca square. Designed by Silvestre Perez in 1798 from his position in *Academia de San Fernando*, that church, which had always attracted his father's attention for his stark and brutalist nature¹², was a reference for Peña. Among other features, he valued the way the author had adapted the enormous building to its location, and the way he had placed the vault top on the intersection of existing urban axis, setting a porch and a stairway in front of the massive structure for the purpose of transition between the scale of the church and the town.

(Fig. IV) *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua*, showing the base of garages and driveways on the foreground. Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

It is precisely from the church that Peña adopts the way to join the new residential block to the street using a platform as a base; this joining mechanism is due to the topography of the site. The site runs parallel to Domingo de Ibaibarriaga Street which, starting in Churruca Square, goes up westwards along the north side of the church, right down the public space extending behind its apse. The location of the plot, 4 m above the street level, raised a dilemma either to lower it to the sidewalk level or keep it at its own level. Finally the latter option is adopted, locating the houses on a base housing the garages, which appear sculpted by the stairway, connecting the street with the doorways. (Fig IV)

Despite the fact that both the memory of the project and most of the texts that accompany the information about this work show his negative to digging as a priori decision as the result of his interpretation of the site, what it is true is that the first project Peña presented for Ibaibarriaga Street shows a horizontal plane on the street level. It was not until he realised that earthworks were economically unviable that he decided to stagger the building in order to adjust it to the terrain and the slope.

What we can see from the very outset is the tooth shaped of the plan (Fig. V), the outcome of the turn of each housing unit which results in a fragmented volume with a broken cornice. It is not clear whether this decision was adopted deliberately with the idea of breaking the impressive character of a unitary project, hard to fit in the centre of a town with an organic growth such as Motrico's, or whether it was taken due to the inclination of the edge of the site on meeting the existing building. In any case, the solution taken, apart from favouring the integration of the volumes, also provided the views from the housing windows with a greater distance to the wall of the church. This solution was not entirely new for Peña, although it was the first time he had implemented the shifting of each housing unit, consequently fragmenting the unity of the stairway. In two of his earlier proposals for blocks made up of symmetric successions of two housing units per landing, the shifting of a doorway from the next had helped him in his first proposal (*Zelai Ondo*, Zarauz 1959) to break the linearity of the façade with which he defines the limit of urban space and in the second one (the housing unit built for Esteban Orbeagozo in Zumarraga in 1960), to adjust it to the site lay-out by means of partial setbacks between neighbouring blocks.

(Fig. V) Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua. Planta del conjunto. Archivo Peña Ganchequi.

But the layout of the floor plan for the *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua*, as it is developed in a modulated way, due to the limited gap the front of a single house presents, and as it results in a shift in heights, identifies with a third proposal he made, which was not built in this case, the project to build 6 *viviendas Beitia*, whose construction was planned to be carried out next to the port of Motrico, on the south slope beginning in the port. In this project, he intended to place the houses obliquely to the slope of the site, staggering uphill, which resulted in a fragmentation of the volume arising from the setback of a bay with regard to the adjacent.

The solution was literally in line with the recommendation made by one of the few books Peña purchased during his university studies: *Town design*, by Frederick Gibberd, who in chapter 12, devoted to *houses on a slope* recommended: 'one of the oldest and quite the nicest ways of climbing the slope is to project one house in front of his neighbour, in such a way that the roof slope combines from house to house without a break.' The varied composition of openings and gaps this device provides is in contrast to the one a linear block would give. This tool will help in *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua* to guarantee a greater integration of the volume in the physiognomy of Motrico.

(Fig. VI) Viviendas Beitia (Mutriku, 1960) and illustration of Town Design by Frederick Gibberd.

Subsequent sketches and proposal made for the construction of the houses of Aizpurua's awarded work on the orchard owned by his family, shows Peña's increasing concern to fragment the immediacy of the block, combining the changes of the floor plans with height differences, and later the single compositions of openings with varied and organic combinations of openings and verandas. (Fig. VII). It could be said that Peña, on bearing so much responsibility (in a site owned by his family, in the town centre and opposite the work of his admired Silvestre Perez), feels the need to vanish, to become part of the old town while his proposal fades away through volumetric and compositional resources which bring closer the image of his building to the image of the neighbouring buildings¹³. A device he would use skilfully again years later in Motrico (which served him as a research laboratory) in the housing developments of *Casas Rosas*, resorting to a painstaking work of volumetric juxtaposition and fragmentation which makes them blend with the volumetric appearance of the town centre, whose building mass shows a fragmented building envelope as a result of gradual building over time¹⁴.

(Fig. VII) Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua. First phase elevation sketches sequence. Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

An organic solution

The resource of fragmentation, establishing proportions in agreement with the organic growth of the old town, favoured as well the organic evolution of the architecture intervention, whose 20 dwellings distributed in three stairwell units were identified as if were a single block, despite having been built in two phases (during the first one, 13 dwellings in 2 units completed later on with a group of 7 dwellings), with two associated developers (Churruca and Iparraguirre). Apart from the discontinuity that could have resulted from its construction in two phases, the image of the housing scheme is unitary despite the fragmentary nature of the volume, thanks to the solutions Peña provides in order to withstand balcony parapets. He connects the overhangs of the different floors by means of a rhythmic succession of steel profiles, which constitute a virtual envelope as a whole, and which give continuity to the array of verandas.

(Fig. VIII) Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua. Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

It was the first constructed solution to an element he provided and to which he will return repeatedly in future works and which will be key in the making of *Casa Arrigain* and *12 viviendas Urresti*. On providing the definition of a virtual uniform and continuous façade, a kind of *low-tech* curtain-wall over the balconies, he frees the openings of their roles in the closure composition. In the words of Fullaondo, through the overlapping layers device, Peña implies subtly 'the possibility of constructive transfiguration of the graphic device of the farmhouses framework,

suggesting in the delicate epithelial tissues (...) a mere reference, an indigenous version of the *neo-liberty* movement'.¹⁵

This layered envelope applied in *Viviendas Arrigain* in a fragmented way all over the façade (Fig. VIII) enables Peña to establish, if virtually, a continuity between the façade and the building roofing, (necessary to avoid the anachronistic image of the farmhouse) without renouncing the use of eaves, providing the building with a larger finishing touch, like a continuous gallery which results from the structural need to fix the railing (solved by means of horizontal planks) while resisting tipping with the best light feeling. The description Peña makes in the narrative of the *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua* on referring to the composition of façades and roofing, leaves no doubt about his intention to use these resources when he states that 'this aspect has been dealt with carefully in order to fit the future construction properly in the town centre. The existing houses in Motrico do not have clearly defined invariants. There abounds, however, the continuous balcony as a decorative element and under the eave, which is frequent in the Basque Country. These elements have been used forming a variety that can be seen in the elevations. This along with the gable roof made of Arabic tiles and the dividing walls makes the resulting architectural volume not to clash with the rest'.¹⁶

Apart from this solution based on the continuity of façade and roof, that he used in numerous projects after the construction of *Arrigain* and *Urresti*, Peña developed other formulas to respond to one of his obsessions: finding a way to stop the eave disrupting the single reading of the volume of the building and to stop it provide the unwanted figurative image of the archetype of a traditional house. One of his most widely used solutions was to establish a real continuity between both elements, eliminating eaves while making the roof slip over the façade until it defines a horizontal transition, which is the solution he came up with in the project of *Olazabal* (1963, built during the period earlier referred to as transition) and which was fully attained in *Aizetzu* in 1964. Rounding off the quartet of prototyped works constructed that year, *Casa Imanolena* could also be included in this group as it provides a third way to solve the transition between roof and façade, providing the roof with autonomy. The roof in some cases is perched as if floating in the void, as in the detached house previously mentioned (solution he will resort to again in the 80's with *Bankoa's* headquarters in Vitoria and the subsidized houses in *Carabanchel*) and in other reaches total autonomy covering the whole building, as in *San Francisco* church, built in Vitoria in 1969.

The framework resulting from the steel profiles Peña places on the front of the balconies overlapping fragmentally over the solid shaft bored by vertical openings and which follow an organic geometry is reminiscent of *Casa alle Zattere* built by Gardella in Venice in 1958, a well-known example of the blending of tradition and modernity. Made up of the asymmetry of balconies and vertical openings looking on to the canal, this modern house is a tribute to Venetian palaces. Peña himself made this reference, in the book *Coversaciones* by Santiago Roqueta¹⁷, when he explained the presence of the vertical openings to the 'influence in that time of the architectural successes of these solutions in other places such as Gardella's, who in those days exerted a significant cultural influence on us'. On his continuous attempt to integrate the building in its environment, he adds, to the vertical openings, shutters, whose ending and colour provide a new element of connection with popular architecture.

Overcoming the Modern Movement

Once the need to respect the 5 fundamentals of Le Corbusier is overcome in order to adhere to the modern principles, we can identify the modern premises Peña does not want to renounce (in his personal adaptation of the Modern Movement to the rules imposed by the cultural, climatic and aesthetic context he has to act on) in the premises referred to in 1965 by Carlos Flores as the essence of the new approach architecture requires.

In his article 'Overcoming the Modern Movement'¹⁸, Carlos Flores warned against the risks of underestimating the masters of modernity, succumbing to the temptation of 'replacing them with old fashioned formulas based on the personality cult of the architect and which prioritize form over any other aspect of the architectural processes'. Carlos Flores, in what he calls 'an attempt to synthesize the basic notions deriving from the written, designed or constructed works' by these masters, lists out 5 aspects which can be found in Peña's works: The programmatic aspect (the demand for a clear and detailed programme of needs), the functional aspect (complying with the natural and spiritual functions) the technological one (suitable solutions to the available resources which minimize maintenance costs) the artistic and cultural one (guaranteeing that the physical and spatial formal expression is in agreement with the ways of thinking and feeling of each culture) and the sociological one (architecture, as art at the service of society, must pursue to bring dignity to the individual).

In the group of houses we are talking about, in which the artistic and cultural aspect lies with the formal approaches already mentioned, it is the layout of the floor plan which provides the fulfilment of all the other aspects. The programmatic and functional ones are dealt with by a clear organisation outline (which separates sleeping, living and service areas) and by the way kitchen and bathroom are gathered in the centre of the floor plan (separating the three bedrooms facing north from the living and dining rooms facing south), while freeing the perimeter of the dwelling, which can be gone through circularly due to the connection between kitchen, dining and living rooms.

(Fig. IX) Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua. Second phase floor plan. Archivo Peña Ganchequi.

The gathering of bathroom-kitchen follows the principle of rationality of the technological aspect (as it allows the use of one single drainpipe and reduces the layout of the domestic water system). This aspect is completed by the accuracy of the structural solution, which establishes an organised network of supports which defines frames parallel to the façade with small spans between them, in line with the prevailing economic conditions. The simple and economical structure arising from its clear and coherent organisation is the common denominator in Peña's architecture, as can be particularly seen in his early works, in which the lack of financial means brought on austerity to them. A specially relevant example of this is *Casa Imaz* (Motrico, 1962), another work constructed during the previously mentioned artistic maturation, in which a parallel series of identical bearing walls made of white bricks, houses a sequence of spaces which make up the house.

Regarding the sociological aspect, his inclination to dignify the individual is clearly reflected in the narrative of the design as the layout of the house intends to find 'large and agreeable spaces providing a feeling of comfort, very important in our opinion when dealing with 80 m² or smaller houses' and encourages 'the appeal of light, space and spatial interaction with nature, attained through the gallery occupied by living-dining rooms and kitchen, providing a feeling of relief and wellness on entering the hall.'

Epilogue

In 1963, the year closing this transition period towards a new way of dealing with architecture, Peña builds the third module of *Viviendas del Premio Aizpurua*, completing the work which started in 1961. Basically he repeats in it the principles which guided the construction of the other two in the first phase. However, some signs emerge which show he has gained confidence in the years passed since the start of the project. The most remarkable one is the change he introduces in the last element of the sequence, modifying the position of the virtual projecting gallery, and introducing a turn in the volume which defines the corner. The gallery, projecting at first and ending through an extension running along the perimeter, takes the dimension of a tower, behaving like an autonomous element of medieval reminiscence which is enhanced by a greater staggering of the elevation (due to the fact that there is an increase in the slope in this part of the street). The tower seems to join the one of Asunción Church allowing Peña at last to speak on the same footing with Silvestre Perez.

The end of this stage of transition, which is the prelude to the fruitful 1964, takes place on the occasion of his brief stay at the Town Planning Department of San Sebastian, in which coinciding with the centenary of the demolition of the city walls, he builds the public space named *Plaza de la Trinidad* (Fig. X), giving meaning to the urban void emerging between the differing boundaries which make up the rear façades of such different buildings as Santa Maria and San Telmo Churches, the houses on 31 de Agosto street and Mount Urgull, which in this part looked fragmented, showing the remains of earlier interventions already obsolete.

(Fig. X) Plaza de la Trinidad (Donostia, 1963). Archivo Peña Ganchegui.

Plaza de la Trinidad marks a turning point in Peña's career, as it is the first work with a subject matter different from that of housing, and as it has the will to blend in with the surroundings and the need to learn to listen to what these surroundings tell it. This work will make a broader impact due to the time it occurs and to the thematic element chosen: Basque rural sports. All these aspects will help him to go deeper into his roots in order to make the right interpretation of the places he is acting upon at a time when he is finishing constructing his first works designed two years before. He has the opportunity to verify on the spot the effectiveness of the resources used and to prove his skill providing each surrounding with a different response. 'It is very different, for instance, to construct in the port of Motrico or in the town centre or to do so outside the town, because these are three cultures, three ways of being and understanding life: that of the fisherman, the town dweller and the farmer'¹⁹

Besides, the time was particularly appropriate because Jorge Oteiza had just published his book *Quosque Tandem ... Essay on the aesthetic interpretation of the Basque soul*, which claims the existence of a Basque style reflected in the cultural and historical specificity of its people and which triggered the process of the cultural and artistic reconstruction of the Basque country crystallising in the creation of the artistic group *Gaur*²⁰ and the cultural movement *Ez Dok Amairu* three years later. Both actively continued during the 70s through initiatives which intended to recover and renew the badly treated Basque cultural life by means of the creation of a *Basque School of Contemporary Art*. A project which reserved for Luis Peña Ganchegui a prominent role as head of the architectural dimension, and which enabled him to follow up his mission to repay his people for the learning acquired and to reward those who had enthusiastically sacrificed themselves for him.

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Footnotes

1. PEÑA, Rocio, SANGALLI, Mario. *Luis Peña Ganchegui Arquitecturas 1958-1994 Arkitekturak*. UPV/EHU . Donostia, 1994.
2. Inverted commas of this paragraph taken from the article 'When architecture wants to be the landscape' written by Rafael Moneo for the catalogue *Luis Peña Ganchegui Arquitecturas 1958-1994 Arkitekturak* made by Rocio Peña and Mario Sangalli on the occasion of the anthological exhibition of the work of Luis Peña Ganchegui which was held at the School of Architecture in San Sebastián.
3. Such was Peña's feeling that he will even ask his friend and colleague, Fernando Higuera, in a letter sent to thank him for his words of congratulation on a recently published article about one of his works in *Hogar y Arquitectura* magazine to do always so, 'so it helps me not to betray my country and those who enthusiastically sacrificed themselves for me'.
4. Vista Alegre tower, in addition to being reviewed on 15th issue of *Arquitectura* magazine published by Madrid College of Architects and being included in the book *Arquitectura Española Contemporánea* by Carlos Flores in 1961 had some impact abroad as it was selected by Cesar Ortiz Echagüe for publication in a Swiss magazine called *Werk* in 1962. It was also recommended by Josep Maria Sostres to be included in *Arquitectura* 63, published by The School of Architecture of Barcelona on occasion of the 7th International Students of Architecture Meeting held in Barcelona in 1963. It got favourable reviews which help him become a member of the selected group of architects culturally active in Madrid and Barcelona. This contributed to creating a third pole of architectural development in San Sebastián, which in a way emulated the third pillar, the northern group, in the dispute between the eastern and central groups in the Group of Architects and Technicians for the Progress of Contemporary Architecture (GATEPAC) and which brought about a thaw in the relations between them.

5. Inspired by Baroja, and bearing a liberal and undogmatic attitude Peña will appreciate in the Basque culture the sober and humble identity of its ancient tradition compatible with a universal concept and a long way from traditional folkloric interpretations.
6. Some golden years in which the importance of Basque architects was in some cases greater than that of their Madrilian and Barcelonian counterparts, as it is proved by the fact that Aizpurua and Vallejo were the only Spanish architects to participate in Basilea's meeting, in which among others M.Breuer, Le Corbusier, H Haring, A Sartoris and S Giedion took part and which served as a preparation for the 2nd CIAM held in Frankfurt in 1929 which had as a single issue for discussion 'Minimum Subsistence Dwelling' (from SANZ Esquidel, Jose Angel, 'El periodo heroico de la arquitectura moderna en el País Vasco (1928-1930)', *Ondare* n° 23, 2004).
7. Promoted by Oriol Bohigas and Carlos de Miguel, The Small Architectural Conferences were a series of mainly Spanish architects' meetings, although there were also some foreign ones (especially Italian and Portuguese) who periodically met during the 60s in several Spanish cities except in the last but one held in the Portuguese town of Tomar.
8. A model of development widely used on the outskirts of Madrid (in some cases successfully carried out, carelessly and unsuccessfully in others) in the second half of the 50s and which was systematically and profusely used in the plan for preparation of building land in the province of Guipuzcoa, fostered by the National Housing Institute in 1959. The catalogue of the exhibition included plans for Motrico, Zumaya, Oyarzun-Renteria and Zarauz made by Peña in collaboration with other architects.
9. An evolution which coincides with the one Ignasi de Sola-Morales refers to in his article 'Arquitectura y existencialismo: una crisis de la arquitectura moderna' published in the 5th issue of *Annals d'arquitectura* magazine (Barcelona, 1991). De Sola-Morales regards the incorporation of the existentialist thinking into architecture as one of the turning points which made rethink the prevailing ethic and aesthetic viewpoints in architecture in the early days of the modern movement and which brought about the change of direction taken by architecture after the Second World War. The influence exerted by Heidegger's discourse on the young revisionists of the Modern Movement with his reference to human, spiritual and emotional aspects; to the defence of the local and vernacular sphere against the global and universal one, and his bet on housing and its interaction with the community as the main purpose for architectural activity, all these factors according to Sola-Morales resulted in a drift towards organicism in contrast with mechanicism. 'two metaphors with which the making of architecture seeks a formal model that allows a unifying explanation.
10. Building so-called, after it was awarded the first Aizpurua prize in 1965. This award is Gipuzcoa's precedent of the COAVN Prizes, an award granted to the best architecture works made in the province on a biennial basis.
11. Coderech, Jose Antonio. 'No son genios lo que necesitamos ahora' *Domus* n° 384, Milano November 1961.
12. It was his father's comments on the Asunción church which awakened an early vocation for architecture.
13. The effectiveness of the fragmentation technique and its conscious use to adapt it to the environment is even more clearly seen if we compare this project with the 8 viviendas Ramirez (Fig. II) that Peña designed a year later in San Sebastián, in which an almost identical house distribution repeated linearly and without setbacks, is accompanied by a façade defined by the repetition of the continuous parapets. This facade is separated from the terrain by pilotis and ended by means of the last parapet as if it were a heavy slab from which chimneys and the volumes housing the staircase units emerge creating a housing block of a clearly Le Corbusierian style.
14. This fragmentation which characterises the sea of roofs covering the whole urban setting, the historic centre of the town, is particularly relevant in Motrico due to its rugged topography. This will lead Peña to regard the roofs of buildings on slope as a fifth façade but not as a surface to regain as a roof terrace (following le Corbusier principles) but as an envelope, whose presence plays a leading role as any of the vertical elements of the building and which needs a well considered implementation.
15. FULLONDO, Juan Daniel, 'Luis Peña Ganchegui, Ironía y Cultura'. *Nueva Forma*, n°53, Madrid, 1970.
16. A concern Peña has to adapt his architecture to the environment, which did not seem to be common among his colleagues as can be inferred from the demands made by Coderch in 1961, already mentioned, or the demand Josep Maria Sostres included in his article 'Algunas premisas para el futuro' which appeared in *Arquitectura* 63 (published by the ETSAB on the occasion of the 7th International Architecture Students' Meeting, held in Barcelona in 1963) and in which he denounced 'the lack of articulation between the building and the surrounding environment' and concluded that considering an architecture work independent of its environment was the general rule in those days.
17. ROQUETA, Santiago. *Luis PEÑA Ganchegui, Conversaciones*, Editorial Blume, Barcelona 1979 ISBN 84-7031-106-9.
18. FLORES, Carlos 'La superación del Movimiento Moderno', *Hogar y Arquitectura*, n°58, Madrid 1965.
19. Luis Peña Ganchegui interviewed for the television programme EITB KULTURA, *EITB* 2005.
20. A group of Gipuzcoa's artists built around Oteiza's figure and which was followed by the creation of other groups such as Orain, Emen and Danok in Alava, Vizcaya and Navarra respectively and making up between them the so-called *Euskal Eskola*.

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Biography

Architect by the ETSA of Barcelona in 1990, PhD by the ETSA of Donostia in 2013 (thesis *Luis Peña Ganchequi: El Arquitecto como Lugar*). Collaborator of Luis Peña Ganchequi from 1988, founded together with him and his daughter, Rocío Peña, the firm "Peña Ganchequi y Asociados" in 1991. Professor of Architectural design since 1997 at the ETSA of Donostia, where he has held various management positions. Founding Member of *Kolektibolektibo* and *Archivo Peña Ganchequi*, he has published, together with Rocío Peña, *Luis Peña Ganchequi. Arquitecturas 1958-1994* (UPV/EHU, 1994) and *Luis Peña Ganchequi. Arquitecto - Premio Munibe, 1997* (Gobierno Vasco, 1999).

Illustrations

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